

EXPLORING THE POTENTIAL OF MUSTARD LEAVES (*Brassica juncea*) AND RADISH (*Raphanus sativus*) AS FOOD FORTIFICATION IN NOODLE MAKING

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the potential of mustard leaves (*Brassica juncea*) and radish (*Raphanus sativus*) as fortification agents in noodle making. By incorporating pureed mustard leaves and radish into traditional noodle recipes, the research aimed to enhance the nutritional profile and sensory appeal of the noodles. The methodology included the preparation of mustard and radish purees, their incorporation into noodle dough, and the subsequent evaluation of the developed products through sensory assessments and nutritional analysis. Sensory evaluations, conducted with 120 respondents across various age groups, indicated high acceptability of the fortified noodles in both pancit guisado and pancit lomi dishes, with consistently high ratings in aroma, color, texture, and taste. Nutritional analysis revealed that the fortified noodles had favorable levels of crude fiber, protein, and fat, suggesting potential health benefits. Marketability assessments highlighted strong consumer demand, sufficient supply availability, and manageable production costs. The findings suggest that mustard leaves and radish can effectively enhance the nutritional value and acceptability of noodles, presenting significant opportunities for commercialization and further culinary innovation. Recommendations include commercial production, expansion of recipe applications, nutritional labeling, supply chain partnerships, and ongoing consumer feedback integration to ensure the product's success in the market.

Keywords: *Food fortification, noodle making, sensory evaluation, nutritional value, mustard leaves, radish*

INTRODUCTION

“As creatures with a body, we should all be peculiarly solicitous with the quality of air, water, and food that we permit into our bodily vehicles” - Bryant McGill.

Consumers are critical evaluators of food, driven by a desire for products that meet their personal preferences and satisfaction. From aroma to appearance, taste, and texture, every aspect of food is scrutinized. One significant issue impacting individuals of all ages today is nutrient deficiency, which slowly deteriorates the immune system, leading to an increased risk of illnesses (World Health Organization, 2020). Concurrently, the evolution of instant or pre-cooked foods has gained popularity, especially among time-conscious individuals. However, efforts are being made to counter the potential negative implications of consuming foods with minimal or lacking nutrients through food fortification.

Food fortification, defined as the addition of key vitamins and minerals to staple foods, is viewed as the most effective and sustainable strategy to increase the nutrient contents of food (Solon, n.d.). This approach is particularly crucial in addressing the micronutrient deficiencies that affect a significant portion of the global population.

Noodles, a staple food in many Asian countries, have gained international recognition, with global consumption on the rise. Researchers are exploring the potential of noodle fortification as a public health intervention to enhance their nutritional characteristics. Attributes such as taste, nutrition, convenience, safety, longer shelf life, and reasonable price have contributed to the popularity of noodles (Hou, 2010).

Noodles originated in China as early as 5000 BC and subsequently spread to other Asian countries such as Japan, Thailand, Korea, and Malaysia (Lee et al., 2008). Wheat flour noodles are a significant part of the diet for many Asians and are favored by many people of all ages (Afalla, 2010).

Modern consumers worldwide face increased risks of various diseases such as diabetes, high cholesterol, cardiovascular diseases, high blood pressure, and irregular blood sugar levels. These risk factors are often associated with diets low in essential nutrients like dietary fiber, phytochemicals, and antioxidants. Functional foods, which provide health benefits and help prevent diseases by incorporating essential nutrients, have become increasingly important (Suman & Rajinder, 2015).

In the Philippines, noodles are a staple food for many families, often consumed throughout the day. Working individuals, in particular, favor noodles due to their convenience and quick preparation, requiring only 2-3 minutes of boiling or rehydration with boiling water. This practice has contributed to the Philippines ranking in the top 7 for instant noodle consumption worldwide (World Instant Noodles Association, 2019). However, nutritionists caution that instant noodles do not meet the body's nutritional requirements (Bhat et al., 2010). Consequently, food manufacturers are responding to consumer demands for higher fiber content by developing products with high-fiber

ingredients. Dietary fiber can also enhance foods' functional properties, such as increasing water-holding capacity, oil-holding capacity, emulsification, and gel formation (Nelson, 2001).

Mustard leaves, primarily grown for their seeds and known for their medicinal properties, belong to annual herbaceous plants with long, branched stems and clusters of yellow flowers (Couplan, 2012). Radish, a significant root and leafy vegetable, is used in salads, as fresh vegetables, cooked, canned, pickled, or eaten raw. Its leaves and sprouts are also consumed in salads or cooked. In traditional medicine, radishes are used to treat coughs, cancer, whooping cough, gastric discomfort, liver disorders, constipation, dyspepsia, gallbladder disorders, arthritis, gallstones, and kidney stones (Adams, 2008).

Given the universal appeal of wheat flour noodles, especially among younger ages, this study aims to find alternative nutrient sources by incorporating mustard leaves and radish into noodles. Noodles fortified with mustard leaves and radish are anticipated to provide Filipinos with nutritious food alternatives rich in fiber, potentially addressing various diseases. Additionally, the development of this fortified food product could offer economic benefits to consumers, farmers, and entrepreneurs.

Research Questions

This study was conducted to determine the acceptability of mustard leaves and radish as food fortification in noodle making. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the processes involved in the preparation of mustard leaves and radish as main ingredients in noodle making?
2. What are the nutritional and physico-chemical analysis results of the developed fortified food products?
3. What is the level of acceptability of the developed mustard leaves and radish noodles in pancit guisado dishes and lomi dishes as evaluated by the Food Technology Students, Food Experts, and Consumers? In terms of (a) aroma; (b) color/appearance; (c) texture; and (d) taste?
4. Is there a significant difference among the evaluation of the groups of respondents on fortified food products?
5. What is the level of marketability of mustard leaves and radish noodles as perceived by the groups of respondents
 - a. consumer demands
 - b. supply availability of radish and mustard
 - c. production cost

METHODOLOGY

This developmental research used materials and ingredients described in the tables below.

Materials

Table 3. Tools and equipment used to prepare Mustard Leaves and Radish in Noodle Recipes.

Descriptions					
Preparatory Tools	Measuring Tools	Mixing Tools	Cutting Tools	Cooking Tools	Equipment
Kneading Table	Measuring Cups	Mixing Bowls	Knife	Gas Range	Pasta Maker
Utility Tray	Measuring Spoons	Wooden Spoon	Peeler	Frying Pan	Blender
Spatula	Weighing Scale	Whisk	Chopping Board	Ladle	Dough Roller & Noodle Maker
Flour Sifter					
Rolling Pin					
Serving Bowl					
Serving Plate					

Table 4. Ingredients of Mustard Leaves and Radish Noodle.

Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3
1000 grams All – purpose flour 60 grams mustard pureed 60 grams radish pureed 1 piece egg 2.5 grams salt 50 grams water	800 grams All – purpose flour 70 grams mustard pureed 70 grams radish pureed 1 piece egg 2.5 grams salt 30 grams water	700 grams All – purpose flour 90 grams mustard pureed 90 grams radish pureed 1 piece egg 2.5 grams salt

Data Gathering Instrument

The study employed a sensorial evaluation questionnaire to assess the respondents' perception of the developed noodles. This instrument was chosen for its effectiveness in measuring the acceptability of the products in terms of aroma, color, texture, and taste.

Data Gathering Procedure

The respondents, comprising children, teenagers, adults, and food experts, were asked to perform a sensory evaluation of the developed noodle products. After obtaining permission, the questionnaires were distributed to the evaluators. The researcher

provided instructions on how to complete the questionnaires, ensuring that all respondents understood the process. Once the questionnaires were filled out, they were collected for further analysis. The sensory assessment questionnaire checklist was utilized to compile data on the acceptability of the mustard leaves and radish noodles.

Sensory Evaluation

The finished products were subjected to sensory evaluation by a diverse group of 120 evaluators, who were selected and briefed on how to assess the products using a scorecard with sample codes. Evaluators tasted samples from each dish and provided feedback on appearance/color, aroma, texture, taste, and general acceptability. The collected data were then decoded and analyzed statistically.

The instrument for data gathering included a score sheet using a qualitative analysis method to determine the acceptability of the food products. Responses regarding the level of acceptability of mustard leaves and radish noodle dishes in terms of appearance/color, aroma, texture, and taste were gathered using a Five-point Likert Scale, with the following weight assignments:

Scale	Numerical Rating	Descriptive Rating
5	4.50 – 5.00	Like very much
4	3.50 – 4.49	Like moderately
3	2.50 – 3.49	Like slightly
2	1.50 – 2.49	Neither like
1	1.00 – 1.49	Dislike

This scale allowed for a structured and quantifiable assessment of the sensory attributes of the noodle products, facilitating a comprehensive analysis of their acceptability among the different respondent groups

RESULTS

Product Development

The development of noodle recipes involved several transformative stages, starting from the use of whole mustard leaves and radish to their conversion into purees. Initially, mustard leaves were processed into a smooth mustard puree, while radish underwent a similar process to become radish puree. These purees were then combined to create a unique noodle product. To test the efficacy and appeal of these new noodles, they were incorporated into six different noodle recipes. Specifically, three samples of mustard leaves and radish were used in pancit guisado, a stir-fried noodle dish, and three samples in pancit lomi, a thick noodle soup. Throughout this development, meticulous

observation and analysis were conducted to refine the mustard leaves and radish noodle products, ensuring they met the desired standards.

Procedure

The developmental procedure commenced with the preparation of mustard leaves and radish, which involved washing, chopping, and pureeing the mustard leaves and cleaning, peeling, and pureeing the radish. These purees were then blended into all-purpose flour to form a dough, ensuring an even distribution of the pureed vegetables throughout. This dough was subsequently rolled out and cut into noodles, which were cooked and utilized as the primary ingredients in the prepared noodle recipes. By following this detailed procedure, mustard and radish noodles were successfully created and integrated into traditional Filipino dishes, enhancing their nutritional value and flavor profile.

Preparation of Mustard leaves puree and Radish puree

To prepare mustard leaves puree, first, harvest the mustard leaves from the garden, ensuring they are fresh. Wash the leaves thoroughly under running water to remove any dirt or impurities, and then drain them. Chop the mustard leaves thinly and blend them into a smooth puree using a blender. For the radish puree, wash the radish top root under running water, peel it, and cut it thinly. Puree the radish slices using a blender.

Preparation for Incorporating Mustard Leaves (*Brassica juncea*) and Radish (*Raphanus sativus*) in Noodles as Nutritional Fortification

For utilizing mustard leaves (*Brassica Juncea*) and radish (*Raphanus Sativus*) as food fortification in noodles, begin with *mise-en-place*, organizing all the necessary ingredients and equipment. Measure the ingredients for the noodle dough and combine them in a large mixing bowl according to the standard proportions. Mix the ingredients with your fingertips to form a ball of dough. Place the dough on a lightly floured surface, flatten it slightly, and knead for about 5 minutes until smooth and elastic, adding more flour if needed to prevent sticking. Let the dough rest until it is slightly dry but still pliable. Lightly flour the dough circle and prepare the noodle maker. Insert the dough into the noodle maker, gently press it, and cut it into strips of the desired width. Carefully unfold the strips, sprinkle them with a small amount of flour to prevent sticking, and the noodles are ready for cooking with your desired recipe.

Figure 1. Kneading the dough for about 5 minutes until smooth and elastic

Preparation of Mustard and Radish Noodle Recipes

Pancit Guisado

For Mustard Leaves and Radish Pancit Guisado, begin by sautéing garlic and onion in a pan. Add chicken breast and liver, seasoning with salt and pepper, and cook for 10-15 minutes. Add soy sauce and chicken stock, letting the mixture boil. Incorporate the mustard leaves noodles into the mixture. Add carrots, cabbage, and celery, simmering until the noodles and vegetables are cooked but not overcooked. Transfer the dish to a serving plate, top with hard-boiled eggs and *embutido*, and serve hot.

Figure 2. Pancit Guisado

Pancit Lomi

For Mustard Leaves and Radish Pancit Lomi, start by bringing a pot of water to a boil and blanch the noodles for about 1 minute. Drain and rinse them in cold water. In a pan, heat about 1 tablespoon of oil over medium heat, cook the liver until just done, then remove it and keep warm. In a large pot, heat the remaining tablespoon of oil, add onions and garlic, and cook until softened. Add chicken and cook until lightly browned, then add fish sauce and cook for another minute. Pour in 8 cups of water and bring to a boil. Lower the heat and simmer until the chicken is cooked through. Add the mustard leaves noodles and cook for about 3 to 5 minutes until tender but firm to bite. Add the liver and cook for about 1-2 minutes. Add carrots and cook for about 1 minute, then add cabbage and continue cooking for another minute or until the vegetables are tender but crisp. Combine cornstarch with 1/2 cup cold water, stir to dissolve, and add to the pot, stirring until slightly thickened. Slowly add eggs in a thin stream, allowing them to slightly set before stirring. Serve hot.

Figure 3. Pancit Lomi

Product Evaluation

Evaluation of the products developed by the groups of respondents is shown in the following tables.

Nutritive Value of Mustard Leaves and Uncooked Radish Noodles

Table 5. Nutritive Value of Mustard Leaves and Uncooked Radish Noodles

Lab. No	Sample Description	Crude Protein	Crude Fiber	Crude Fat	Moisture	Ash
		%	%	%	%	%
FT-24-0025	Noodles w/ Mustard & Radish as Food Fortification	9.12	0.13	0.47	38.34	0.56

The table above summarizes the nutritive values of the developed mustard leaves and radish noodles from the Department of Agriculture, Regional Field Office No. 02, Tuguegarao City, Cagayan. The developed mustard leaves and radish noodles have a high crude fiber content of 9.12%, a crude protein content is 0.13%, crude fat content of 0.47%, these noodles are a healthy option for those looking to reduce fat intake. The moisture content is moderately high at 38.34%, which may affect texture and shelf life,

necessitating proper storage. The ash content of 0.56% indicates the presence of beneficial minerals, contributing to the overall nutritional value of the noodles.

Acceptability of Mustard Leaves and Radish Noodles in Two Recipes

Table 6. Level of acceptability of the developed mustard leaves and radish noodles in pancit guisado dishes as evaluated by children, teenagers, adults and noodle experts in terms of aroma, color, texture, and taste.

Product	Criteria	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Sample 1 Pancit Guisado	Aroma	4.6833	0.56484	Like very much
	Color	4.6667	0.55509	Like very much
	Texture	4.6833	0.56484	Like very much
	Taste	4.6833	0.53426	Like very much
	Average	4.6792	0.31786	Like very much
Sample 2 Pancit Guisado	Aroma	4.8000	0.47809	Like very much
	Color	4.8000	0.46018	Like very much
	Texture	4.8333	0.37424	Like very much
	Taste	4.8667	0.34136	Like very much
	Average	4.8250	0.20395	Like very much
Sample 3 Pancit Guisado	Aroma	4.6750	0.55250	Like very much
	Color	4.6750	0.55250	Like very much
	Texture	4.7750	0.49302	Like very much
	Taste	4.7583	0.44901	Like very much
	Average	4.7208	0.27915	Like very much

Table 6 provides a detailed evaluation of the acceptability of developed mustard leaves and radish noodles in "pancit guisado" dishes as assessed by the respondents. The criteria for evaluation include aroma, color, texture, and taste. Each criterion is rated on a scale where a mean score near 5 indicates a high level of acceptability, and the standard deviation measures the consistency of the ratings.

For "Sample 1 Pancit Guisado," the mean scores for aroma, color, texture, and taste are all approximately 4.68, with standard deviations around 0.56, indicating a high and consistent level of acceptance as participants "like very much" this sample in all aspects. The overall average score is 4.6792 with a standard deviation of 0.31786.

"Sample 2 Pancit Guisado" received even higher scores, with means for each criterion ranging from 4.80 to 4.87 and smaller standard deviations (around 0.34 to 0.48), suggesting strong and consistent approval. The average score is 4.8250 with a standard deviation of 0.20395, the lowest among all samples, indicating the highest consistency.

"Sample 3 Pancit Guisado" also scored well, with means between 4.6750 and 4.7750 and standard deviations ranging from 0.44901 to 0.55250, reflecting a high but slightly less consistent level of acceptance compared to Sample 2. The overall average is 4.7208 with a standard deviation of 0.27915.

This implies that mustard leaves and radish noodles can be successfully incorporated into "pancit guisado" with high acceptability and consistency. This has significant implications for enhancing the nutritional value of traditional dishes, opening new culinary avenues, and offering potential market opportunities.

Table 7. Level of acceptability of the developed mustard leaves and radish noodles in *Lomi* dishes was evaluated by children, teenagers, adults, and noodle experts in terms of aroma, color, texture, and taste.

Product	Criteria	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Sample 1 Lomi	Aroma	4.6583	0.57242	Like very much
	Color	4.6250	0.58068	Like very much
	Texture	4.6833	0.56484	Like very much
	Taste	4.6667	0.55509	Like very much
	Average	4.6583	0.34746	Like very much
Sample 2 Lomi	Aroma	4.8167	0.44878	Like very much
	Color	4.8417	0.42989	Like very much
	Texture	4.8333	0.37424	Like very much
	Taste	4.8667	0.36515	Like very much
	Average	4.8396	0.21202	Like very much
Sample 3 Lomi	Aroma	4.7083	0.54071	Like very much
	Color	4.6750	0.56750	Like very much
	Texture	4.7750	0.49302	Like very much
	Taste	4.7667	0.44407	Like very much
	Average	4.7312	0.25139	Like very much

The table provides a detailed evaluation of the acceptability of developed mustard leaves and radish noodles in "pancit lomi" dishes as assessed by food technology students, food experts, and consumers. The criteria for evaluation include aroma, color, texture, and taste. Each criterion is rated on a scale where a mean score near 5 indicates a high level of acceptability, and the standard deviation measures the consistency of the ratings.

For "Sample 1 Lomi," the mean scores for aroma, color, texture, and taste rated 4.6250 to 4.6833, and standard deviations around 0.55 to 0.58, indicating a high level of

acceptance with good consistency. The overall average is 4.6583 with a standard deviation of 0.34746.

"Sample 2 Lomi" achieved the highest ratings overall, with mean scores for each criterion between 4.8333 and 4.8667 and low standard deviations (around 0.37 to 0.45), suggesting very strong and consistent approval. The average score is 4.8396 with a standard deviation of 0.21202.

Lastly, "Sample 3 Lomi" showed mean scores from 4.6750 to 4.7750 with standard deviations around 0.44 to 0.57, reflecting a high but slightly less consistent level of acceptance compared to Sample 2. The overall average is 4.7312 with a standard deviation of 0.25139.

In summary, all samples of lomi using mustard leaves and radish noodles were rated highly, with mean scores indicating that they were "liked very much" across all criteria. Sample 2 generally received the highest and most consistent ratings, which had the highest average scores and the lowest standard deviations, indicating it was the most preferred and consistently liked sample

Comparison in the Level of Acceptability of Mustard and Radish Noodles Used in Two Recipes across Groups of Respondents

Table 8. Comparison in the level of acceptability of mustard and radish noodles as perceived by the evaluators according to their age group.

Products	F-value	p-value	Comparison	Decision	Remark
Sample 1 Pancit Guisado	1.29	0.28	p-value > 0.05	accept Ho	no significant difference
Sample 2 Pancit Guisado	0.33	0.85	p-value > 0.05	accept Ho	no significant difference
Sample 3 Pancit Guisado	2.64	0.05	p-value = 0.05	accept Ho	no significant difference
Sample 1 Pancit Lomi	1.12	0.34	p-value > 0.05	accept Ho	no significant difference
Sample 2 Pancit Lomi	0.13	0.94	p-value > 0.05	accept Ho	no significant difference
Sample 3 Pancit Lomi	2.13	0.10	p-value > 0.05	accept Ho	no significant difference

The table summarizes the results of the statistical analysis used to determine if there is a significant difference in the evaluations of the fortified food products by different groups of respondents. The analysis uses the F-value and p-value to compare the groups, with a p-value threshold of 0.05 for significance.

For "Sample 1 Pancit Guisado," the F-value is 1.29 with a p-value of 0.28. Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis (Ho) is accepted, indicating no significant difference in evaluations among the groups

For "Sample 2 Pancit Guisado," the F-value is 0.33 with a p-value of 0.85. Again, the p-value exceeds 0.05, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis and suggesting no significant difference in the groups' evaluations.

For "Sample 3 Pancit Guisado," the F-value is 2.64 with a p-value of 0.05. Although the p-value is exactly 0.05, it still falls at the threshold, meaning the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating no significant difference.

Regarding "Sample 1 Lomi," the F-value is 1.12 with a p-value of 0.34. The p-value is above 0.05, resulting in the acceptance of the null hypothesis and showing no significant difference in evaluations among the groups.

For "Sample 2 Lomi," the F-value is 0.13 with a p-value of 0.94. The high p-value means the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating no significant difference in evaluations among the groups.

For "Sample 3 Lomi," the F-value is 2.13 with a p-value of 0.10. As the p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted, and there is no significant difference in evaluations among the groups.

In summary, the analysis shows that for all samples of "pancit guisado" and "lomi," there are no significant differences in the evaluations by the different groups of respondents. This conclusion is drawn from p-values that are all greater than 0.05, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis in each case. Thus, the evaluations of the fortified food products are consistent across the different groups, indicating a generally uniform acceptance level among food technology, food experts, and consumers.

Level of Marketability of Mustard Leaves and Radish Noodles

Table 9. Level of marketability of mustard leaves and radish noodles as perceived by children, teenagers, adults, and food experts in terms of consumer demands, supply availability of radish mustard, and production cost.

Category	Respondents	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Consumer Demand	Children	4.92	0.18	Strongly Agree
	Teenager	4.82	0.29	Strongly Agree
	Adult	4.77	0.23	Strongly Agree

	Food experts	4.84	0.24	Strongly Agree
Supply Availability	Children	4.84	0.29	Strongly Agree
	Teenager	4.69	0.29	Strongly Agree
	Adult	4.75	0.26	Strongly Agree
	Food experts	4.87	0.22	Strongly Agree
Production Cost	Children	4.84	0.23	Strongly Agree
	Teenager	4.82	0.24	Strongly Agree
	Adult	4.81	0.24	Strongly Agree
	Food experts	4.84	0.23	Strongly Agree

The table evaluates the marketability of mustard leaves and radish noodles based on the perceptions of different respondent groups concerning consumer demand, supply availability of radish and mustard, and production cost. Each category is assessed using mean scores and standard deviations.

For “consumer demand”, the mean scores are consistently high across all respondent groups, indicating a strong consensus that there is high consumer demand for these products. Children have the highest mean score of 4.92 with a standard deviation of 0.18, suggesting a very strong agreement and low variability in responses. Teenager follows with a mean of 4.82 and a standard deviation of 0.29, while adult has a mean of 4.77 and a standard deviation of 0.23. Food experts' mean is 4.84 with a standard deviation of 0.24. All these means fall into the "Strongly Agree" category, signifying that all groups believe consumer demand for the product is very high.

Regarding “supply availability”, the scores also indicate strong agreement across all groups that the supply of radish and mustard is sufficient. Children’s mean is 4.84 with a standard deviation of 0.29, showing strong agreement. Teenager has a slightly lower mean of 4.69 but maintains a similar standard deviation of 0.29. Adult's mean is 4.75 with a standard deviation of 0.26, and Food experts 's mean is the highest at 4.87 with a standard deviation of 0.22. Again, all groups fall within the "Strongly Agree" category, reflecting confidence in the availability of necessary supplies.

For “production cost”, the respondent groups also show strong agreement that the production cost is manageable. Children and Food Expert both have a mean of 4.84 with a standard deviation of 0.23, indicating a very strong consensus. Teenager has a mean of 4.82 and a standard deviation of 0.24, while Adult has a mean of 4.81 with a standard deviation of 0.24. The means for production cost across all groups fall into the "Strongly Agree" category, suggesting that respondents believe the production cost is favorable for marketability.

In summary, the perceived marketability of mustard leaves and radish noodles is very high among the respondent groups. They strongly agree on the high consumer demand, adequate supply availability, and favorable production costs. The consistently high mean scores across all categories and groups, coupled with low standard deviations, indicate a strong, unanimous perception that these products are highly marketable.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that mustard leaves (*Brassica juncea*) and radish (*Raphanus sativus*) hold significant promise as food fortification agents in noodle making. The product development process, which involved transforming these vegetables into purees and incorporating them into noodle recipes, resulted in a unique and nutritious noodle product. Sensory evaluations, including aroma, color, texture, and taste, consistently indicated high acceptability across different age groups and expertise levels, particularly in pancit guisado and pancit lomi dishes. Furthermore, the nutritional analysis revealed favorable levels of crude fiber, protein, and fat, indicating potential health benefits. Marketability assessments also highlighted strong consumer demand, ample supply availability, and manageable production costs, further supporting the feasibility of commercialization. Overall, this study highlights the potential of mustard leaves and radish as nutritional fortification agents in noodles, paving the way for future exploration and adoption in the food industry.

Recommendations

In consideration of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following are forwarded as recommendations:

1. Given the high acceptability and positive nutritional profile, manufacturers should consider commercializing mustard leaves and radish-fortified noodles. This could include

marketing campaigns highlighting their health benefits and unique flavors to attract health-conscious consumers.

2. The range of recipes should be expanded incorporating mustard leaves and radish noodles beyond traditional Filipino dishes like pancit guisado and pancit lomi. Experiment with other popular dishes and cuisines to broaden market appeal.

3. Nutritional content should be clearly labeled on the packaging to inform consumers about the benefits of these fortified noodles. Educational campaigns can help raise awareness about the importance of fiber, protein, and reduced fat content in daily diets.

4. A consistent supply of fresh mustard leaves and radishes should be ensured by partnering with local farmers. This can help maintain the quality of the noodles and support the agricultural community.

5. Further research should be conducted on the shelf life and optimal storage conditions of these noodles to enhance their texture and longevity, given their high moisture content.

6. Extensive market testing should be conducted in various demographic segments to gather more detailed consumer feedback. Use this feedback to refine the product further and improve its marketability.

7. Cost-effective production methods should be explored to keep the noodles affordable while maintaining quality. This includes optimizing the puree-to-flour ratio and streamlining the production process.

8. Collaboration with health and wellness organizations like the DOST, and FDA should be done to promote noodles as a healthy food option. This can help build credibility and expand the product's reach.

9. Innovative and eco-friendly packaging solutions should be invested to highlight the product's nutritional benefits and appeal to environmentally conscious consumers.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher hereby assures that the study was conducted in strict adherence to research ethical standards, ensuring that participants provided informed consent, had the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, their anonymity was preserved, their well-being was protected, no conflict of interest influenced the study, plagiarism was

rigorously avoided, findings were interpreted without bias, and the results were used exclusively for research purposes.

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